

The adoption of digital twin technology to facilitate resource and asset tracking in field service management: a conceptual model

This paper is Systematic Literature Review using Barbara Kitchenham methods.

We provided **.ris** file after conducted 3 stage of Barbara Kitchenham methods on attached

Review Method

This paper utilises a methodological framework based on Barbara Kitchenham's research [13], which enables a systematic approach to selecting articles and conducting thorough content evaluation. The focus is on integrating assets and resource tracking via digital twin technologies.

Figure 1 provides an outline of the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) process, which includes the stages of planning, conducting, and reporting. A research protocol will be made to provide comprehensive guidance on multiple areas of the review, such as research inquiries, search methodologies, criteria for selecting studies, assessment of quality, extraction of data, and techniques for synthesis.

Fig. 1. Kitchenham systematic literature review flow process

Research Questions

The subsequent research questions are related to this paper:

- How does digital twin technology enhance the efficiency and efficacy of resource allocation in field service management (FSM)?
- What approaches may be used to maximise the benefits of digital twin technology for asset management and monitoring in the field service management (FSM) domain?

We will create a comprehensive study strategy based on the research topics to evaluate how Digital Twin technology could improve asset and resource management tracking. This study's limits must be acknowledged. English-language works from 2019–2023 will be our focus. Important publications, including reviews, conference proceedings, and research articles, will be prioritised.

Searching Approach

To assess the existing literature, the literature search progressively narrowed down to scholarly journals that specifically explore the commercial dimensions of digital twin technology, with a particular emphasis on asset and resource management and the resolution of difficulties faced by Field Service Management (FSM). The author investigated using well-known digital resources such as Scopus, IEEE Xplore Digital Library, Science Direct,

Springer Link, and Google Scholar [14]. To ensure a methodical and thorough approach, we have developed a research protocol, as shown in Table 1, which will serve as the foundation for the succeeding phases of this study.

Fig. 2. Searching Protocol

Studi Selection

To facilitate the process of selecting journals, the researchers made use of Mendeley - a software for managing references. The software can be found at www.mendeley.com. The primary articles were selected from established journals that specifically address the asset and resource aspects associated with digital twin technologies. The process involved evaluating titles and abstracts to eliminate certain primary research, followed by a subsequent round of exclusion based on a thorough review of the full text to determine the final selection of studies.

Data Extraction

From the selected research, a total of 36 papers have been specifically picked for inclusion in each round. These papers will be thoroughly read and meticulously studied in further detail.

TABLE I. PRIMARY STUDIES SELECTED

Source	Studies Found	Candidate studies	Selected studies
Frontier	5	3	2
IEEE Xplore	10	7	6
ScienceDirect	12	5	4
Emerald	8	3	1
Springer Link	11	8	6
ACM Digital	15	4	2
MDPI	14	11	9
Taylor & Francis	13	3	2
Google Scholars	7	6	4
Total	95	50	36

Data Synthesis

Data synthesis is crucial for exploring research queries, as it entails gathering information from different investigations. By consolidating data, its relevance is amplified, surpassing the limitations of individual findings. This review effectively combines both quantitative and qualitative data, utilizing diverse methodologies to satisfy distinct research objectives. The narrative synthesis process prioritizes the combination of different strands of data. Moreover, a methodical organization of data, encompassing tables, pie charts, and bar charts, proficiently showcases existing trends and difficulties in using digital twin technology, guaranteeing lucidity and precision.

Research finding

We employed a meta-analytical approach to examine the results of specific studies gathered from various publications. Many academic studies have focused on the use of digital twin (DT) technology to improve asset monitoring in the resource and management industries. Scopus continues to maintain its leading position as the main platform for researchers to share their research, providing a vast collection of peer-reviewed publications. Primarily, these publications are in the form of journal papers, with a smaller portion consisting of conference proceedings.

Fig. 3. Selected Studies

Multiple studies have emphasized the collaborative effect of integrating digital twin technology with the tools employed by enterprises to oversee their resources and assets, leading to substantial improvements. In recent years, the adoption of digital twin technology has gained momentum across various industries, revolutionizing the way assets and resources

are managed. Digital twins are transforming resource and asset management in many industries such as infrastructure, healthcare, manufacturing, and transportation. They improve the efficiency of monitoring and boost the management of assets across a range of systems, from industrial facilities to complex infrastructure [15], [16], [17], [18].

Fig. 4. Keyword co-occurrence network of DTs from Selected Studies

A study conducted by Shahzad et al. [15], revealed a significant emphasis on digital asset management where some companies are transitioning from conventional document-oriented procedures to model-oriented, data-centric, and automated asset management processes with the help of Building Information Models (BIM) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) focus on design and construction stages, digital twins excel in boosting operational efficiency by enabling predictive maintenance through real-time data analysis. Making this integration allows for

improved connectivity, geospatial analysis, and visualization, enhancing decision-making processes related to infrastructure construction planning and maintenance [19]. S. Meschini et al [20] found that Digital Twin's integration with the asset management system with the help of AI and machine learning, significantly makes the system's overall performance much better in monitoring and tracking the physical asset and allows organizations to transition from reactive to proactive maintenance strategies, ultimately leading to increased asset lifespan and reduced downtime [21].

In conclusion, the integration of digital twin technology with asset management systems, leveraging tools such as Building Information Models (BIM) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS), and supported by AI and machine learning, marks a transformative approach to asset management, enabling organizations to transition from reactive to proactive maintenance strategies and ultimately enhancing overall system performance.